

Original Article

When We Will Actually “Be There”: Exploring Ethical Guidelines for Immersive Media in Pakistan

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Abstract

The comeback of Immersive media technologies after being sidelined in the 1980's has certainly mesmerized the world. It has made its way into all fields alike, but Immersive Journalism is a center of focus for many. So far, many news agencies and channels around the world have already started immersive journalism including New York Times, Washington Post, Associated Press, Reuters, Vice News, the Guardian, Al Jazeera and El País etc. Although Immersive Journalism has not started in Pakistan yet, bringing news story to the audience “as if they were there” is the next milestone which will soon be achieved by the New Media and journalism Industry of Pakistan as well. The point to ponder for Pakistani media researchers is how our already “struggling to survive” ethical guidelines for visual journalism, will adapt to a framework which may be able to guide journalists and VR content producers about the implications of using content with an increased level of immersion. Truth telling may be made stronger by generating emotional empathy but what about the consequences of spawning fabricated news content and stories which will make the audience believe anything. Working on ethical framework for Immersive journalism is vital for maintaining a balance between technological adaptation and human sanity. The research looks at existing ethical guidelines for editors and journalists in Pakistan along with reviewing the literature being produced internationally on immersive Journalism ethics in light of deontological approach theory and proposes recommendations for production and regulation of such content so we can welcome technology and enjoy the benefits with responsibility.

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Introduction

Journalism is all about collecting useful information and communicating it to the people who need it in a way that they can get most benefit out of it. Like any other communication process, news production also relies heavily on medium and message. The evolution of news industry has gone from delivering news on paper to TV Screens to cell phones and the latest in the row is to the idea of presenting news to audience, as if, they were virtually present in that event, as an experience. NASA Scientist Steven Ellis first established virtual environments as communication media (Ellis, 1991) mainly because of their characteristic of deeply-engaging or “immersing” the audiences. Although use of Immersive virtual media for Journalism is a recent development, they are being used for about a century in a variety of other disciplines (Kaplan-Rakowski, 2019), including entertainment, medicine, warcraft and space studies. Hence Immersive media has been used in all fields in which exposing an actual person in bone and flesh is either too risky or too costly. Immersive media major application has been in entertainment sector where immersive gaming has achieved unimaginable success by transporting people into fairytale lands of their choice and construct as many parallel universes and alternate realities as they can imagine.

Immersive Media is an umbrella term that refers to 360-degree video, Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR) and Mixed Reality (MX) gadgets as well as all immersion-enabled media content (Han, 2019). Speaking in

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strictly technological terms, most Immersive Media transports an audience virtually into another world through first-person interaction with virtual reconstruction of a scene (Kasahara, 2015). An environment that dissolves the screen that keep the conventional media audience safely seated in the comfort of their homes. The thrill of increased interaction creates an immense impact on the audience and enables them to register information as an experience.

Although immersive content has shown a lot of potential in the news industry, the conventional newsroom rather reluctantly gave in to this technological revolution only about a decade ago, when Immersive Journalism research started receiving investments as they were trying to win back the audience that had drifted away from conventional approach of newscasting from a newsroom in favor of the more active news seeking behaviors using social media and internet. (Hermida, 2016) The idea of Immersive journalism initially surfaced in thesis ideas or conference paper presentations in early 2000s but it did not receive much attention until 2010 when journalist like Nonny de la Pena, Sarah Jones, Ana Luisa Sánchez Laws and others realized its potential and started producing truly Immersive Journalistic pieces like ‘Hunger in Los Angeles’ in 2012 and Project Syria (2014).

Immersive Journalism projects are reconstruction of real-life news happening which allows a user to be present in the scene of the happening and experience it as if they were actually there. The most sought-after consequence of relying news in this way is to raise empathy for the victims which is expected to raise the impact of the news (Hassan, 2020). Hence Immersive journalism offers great promise in bringing back the audience that news producers are losing to social media network, but, at what cost? How will this new method of news production reform the Journalistic principles that have always guided news production.

The very foundation of news industry stands on the conjecture of journalistic integrity; that a professionally sound journalist will never compromise on his journalistic duties of truthfulness, accuracy, objectivity, impartiality, fairness, and public accountability while gathering newsworthy information and relying it to public. Having said this, we cannot close our eyes on the ethical challenges and dilemma that the news production industry as well as the journalists deal with on daily basis. Difference of opinion, conflict of interest, biasedness, data privacy, sensitivity of information, privacy versus news value, protecting sources and having to treat audiences as consumers are just to name a few. The addition immersive journalism as a tool in the hands of news producers will present new ethical challenges for the News industry.

The revolutionary impact of Immersive news content is actually posing the biggest hurdle to adaptation of the same as the news producers and journalist feel the burden of ethical disparities and ethical questions that will be raised about the absorption or response of consumer on such content. Another built-in characteristic of a piece of Immersive journalism that goes against journalistic ethics is the reconstruction of the event after it has occurred naturally.

The news industry of Pakistan is always trying to be ‘at par’ with international news agencies both in terms of technology and professional practice, but they are lagging far behind with almost negligible progress in the field of Immersive Journalism. A few corporates are known to have started the setup, but not a single journalistic piece has yet been produced. One of the major challenges to the diffusion of this technology remains scarce availability of gadget manufacturers and their monopoly over the market but more importantly a bigger hurdle is the insecurity of old-time professionals that they may be taken over or lose their jobs or not be able to perform better in a more technological setup. Reluctance towards adoption of new technologies can also be figured out by the lack of local research content available on the subject of immersive media and Immersive journalism. This paper takes the lead in discussing and proposing an anticipatory approach towards this technology and aspires to guide news industry in anticipation of what ethical pressure this technology will build so that our professionals are better prepared to deal with the challenges, and take action in time before the consequences are out of hand and the reluctance of the society grows further. The paper explores the literature to find ethical guidelines available globally and how they may be adapted to fit in Pakistani culture or renovated to take full benefit of the approaching technological revolution.

Literature Review

Adam Thompson argues in his conference paper on immersive morality (Thompson, 2017) that an immersive experience is one’s involvement in a scenario that is void of “real-world consequences”. The job of a conventional journalist has always been to convey news which is newsworthy and has impact on the reader. However, with the advent of social media, conventional newscasting is losing its charm for the audience and newsroom are having to

explore new more interesting ways of telling news stories. The biggest challenge for journalists is to tell compelling stories and to tell them timely. Journalisms have always struggled and adopted new technologies and methods to engage the news readers who later became audiences and are now being referred to as news users or participants. Immersive technologies are at the verge of taking the viewer right into the news, experiencing it as if they were there. Newest in the line being immersive journalism where journalism started to understand the power of Virtual and Augmented reality technologies to enhance audience engagement and tell stories as if the audience were there in the news story experiencing it firsthand (Sundar, 2017)

According to the Reuters news report (2019), newsrooms are facing trouble as the advertising industry is no longer sustaining the conventional news pattern (Hölig, 2019) and that explains the increased attention towards immersive journalism to engage audiences which are much more active in news-seeking approaches. Typically, an immersive news story will be when the audience is virtually transported into a news event by engaging their visual and aural senses where smart Head Mounted Displays respond to body movements like head turning and regenerate video footage on the runtime. (De la Peña, 2010) However, reporters, newsrooms and newspapers are exploring many forms of immersion, all targeted at engaging the audience.

The idea of transporting audiences virtually to the place of happening was first brought forward by Rheingold (1991) and later by Hamit (1993) who discussed the Virtual Reality as the next logical step in communication (Rheingold, 1991). This was the start of the first wave in Immersive Journalism research. Although researchers like Biocca, Levy (1995) along with many others saw a lot of potential in the technology and theorized that Immersion would conquer time and space and will be able to create the illusion of “being there”, (Biocca, 1995) they were not able to break into the conventional newsroom until the second wave that started in 2010.

After about a decade of relatively less activity, the research area started to build momentum again in 2010 when the ideas were once again being discussed in masters’ theses write-ups and conference papers and the coming years saw a serious increase in research investment into the prospects of immersion in news industry (Uskali, Immersive Journalism as Storytelling: Ethics, Production, and Design, 2021). This has opened a floodgate of empirical studies and projects being conducted in the field of Immersive journalism. Melissa Bosworth and Lakshmi Sarah (2019) thoroughly investigate these projects and experiments in their book offering a complete overview of recent explorations in VR, AR and MR for journalistic storytelling (Bosworth, 2018). More recent researchers and journalists are now looking to strengthen their news stories with immersion as it provides the opportunity to experience places and events with your own eyes and ears, without words, which helps them cross cultural and language barriers (<https://reutersinstitute.politics.ox.ac.uk/what-we-can-learn-best-examples-immersive-journalism>).

The total indulgence referred to as immersion of audience in a news story creates empathy which helps raise the impact of the news and enhance newsworthiness. Since 2015 and 2016, a lot of news are being produced using VR, AR, MR, and 360-degree video which aim at transporting audiences to the actual scene and the result is an instant increase in empathy for the news subject. (Constine, 2015). Hunger in Los- Angeles (Bishop, 2013) and Project Syria (Pena, Jan 29, 2014) are the first of many highly impactful examples the of immersive journalism.

Despite the hype it is receiving, the genre of journalism comes with challenges of its own. Where a lot of research has been going on in order to overcome the technological hinges and make Immersive Journalism a mainstream news genre, an equal amount of consideration is going into studying the impact of such content on audiences. The very nature of Immersive content dictates that the story will be a reconstruction of events instead of the conventional relaying of events in their actual state, through video recordings. However, the impact of Immersive news content has been proven to be manifold more than news conveyed through the conventional screen. When visual newscasting started, the ethical guidelines need to be devised thoroughly. The same needs to be done now for immersive journalism.

Immersive content has many different dimensions of study including production, distribution, use and impact of the immersive content (Johnson D. G., 2020). However, when it comes to Journalism, creating empathy is the biggest drive for rapid adoption of immersive technologies, even though concerns prevail about how long-lasting the effects of the empathy will be, how it limits the subject of developed content and how impartiality can be maintained. Sarah Jones (2021) has contributed a generous overview of all the recent Immersive Journalism content and experiences created to study the empathy building process in her book. (Uskali, Immersive Journalism as Storytelling: Ethics, Production, and Design, 2021) .

Albeit immersive Journalism is still in its inception phase, the technology is mature enough for researchers to look back at the impact and work to recommend anticipatory ethics to channel the development of this technology for the good of people (Johnson D. G., 2020).

A multitude of literature raises concerns about ethical issues relating to immersive media in general from the consumer point of view. A study (2019) by Dr. Rohib Kabha consolidates these concerns and points out that immersive media may create Privacy concerns, issues of confidentiality of data, social isolation, potential Abuse and physical hazards, unrealistic expectations and reality distortion along with other Long term effects on human health (Kabha, 2019)

Along with Immersive Media ethics, journalism has ethical constraints for the content producer, in this case the reporter or the journalist. Many researchers are exploring this trajectory to come up with some sort of ethical guidelines for Immersive Journalism. Perez-Seijo & Lopez Garcia (2019) highlight that it is important to redefine ethics for IJ, as some of the production procedures go against conventional standards of transparent journalism (Pérez-Seijo, Five ethical challenges of immersive journalism: A proposal of good practices' indicators. , 2019).

Methodology

The paper under goes a through existing literature study and explores the research being done internationally to propose a framework of anticipatory ethics for adoption of Immersive Media technology in journalism (Pérez-Seijo, Five ethical challenges of immersive journalism: A proposal of good practices' indicators. , 2019). The existing code of ethics of current media outlets and organizations using Immersive journalism were also reviewed, including Al-Jazeera (Code of Ethics. Al Jazeera, 2014), Associated Press (News Values and Principles. Associated Press, 2018), BBC (Violence in News and Current Affairs:Editorial Guidelines., 2018), New York Times (Guidelines on Integrity. New York Times. , 2008) and some others. The context and state of media ethics in Pakistan has been taken into account. Many independent journalistic platforms have tried to structure journalistic guidelines including Pakistan Coalition for Ethical Journalism (PCEJ) (Accountable journalism, 2015), Council of Pakistani newspaper editors (CPNE, 2022) Furthermore, the religious and societal dilemmas that may foster or present a hurdle to the spread of this technology has been studied. Immersive Media ethics are a subject of study for professional practice researcher's all-over the world in journalism however this paper is making its recommendations specifically in Pakistani context.

Discussion

Examining from a deontological lens, every single day in the life of a journalist is an ongoing matter of choosing between journalistic integrity and quick fixes. With advanced photo-editing digital tools, the difference between something happening or not happening is a few minutes of photo editing, and the upcoming technology where emotions will not be created and shattered over actual footage, but over reconstruction of the footage, the profession has become a true test of character and personal integrity, as Abraham Lincoln said, "if you wish to test a man's character, give him power." Likewise, Immersive Journalism is the power which journalists may use or exploit both consciously and unconsciously, unless they are mindful of the reverberations. Researchers all over the globe have always presented anticipatory ethics for upcoming technologies to warn innovators about the possible impact on consumers as well as the society.

Digital journalism and mobile journalism have already raised enough ethical concerns on journalistic integrity that the audience is skeptical. (Friend, 2015) A study in Nigeria rate Fake news as the biggest unethical practice in local news industry. Earlier TV channels claimed responsibility on the content they aired, but the race for higher ratings brought that responsibility down and when social media came, individually monitored local news websites and YouTube channels have very little regulation or accountability left for their reporting, pair that up with what image manipulation software can do, and you have your self the highest possible like, views and share and you can now publish and broadcast anything. (Mihailidis, 2017)

The developed world has come to terms with the changing landscape and they are improvising along the way. Ethical guidelines are being revised and personal credibility is now taking lead as people are following news media professionals as opinion leaders to get news (Hu, (2012, May)). Local media channel and News professionals and anchor persons are increasingly shifting towards social media like YouTube and Twitter to build and maintain their own fan following. (Zulqarnain, 2020). As Immersive journalism is gaining hype in the developed world, we can safely say that Pakistan News Industry will soon venture into the area which makes it even more significant for

researchers to investigate how the technology may blend into the professional practice of journalists as well as the local culture and what ripples it may create for the societal structures or media professionals.

First formal example of Immersive Journalism is project “Gone Gitmo” (2013) by writer, director and journalist Nonny de la Pena and Peggy Weil, artists and professor, which was based on her earlier documentary “unconstitutional”, which is a recreation of Guantanamo Bay prison and talk about the inhumane living conditions provided to the prisoners. Gone Gitmo was followed by other Immersive Journalism projects including Hunger in Los Angeles, project Syria, Fight for Falluja, Frontline, Yemen’s strike of Terror, 12 seconds of gunfire and many others. The main focus of most Immersive journalism projects has been to raise empathy for the people in suffering.

With all this work going on the international scenario, Pakistan is still struggling to comprehend the magnitude of the technology.

The complete spectrum of ethical issues that may present themselves as the immersive technology matures is multifaceted on cannot be studied with a linear approach. After reviewing the existing literature, the discussion may be presented from the perspective of consumer of the content as well as the practitioner or manufacturer of content i.e., the journalist.

Ethical Issues Faced by Consumers of Immersive Content

Guarding Consumer’s Privacy

The biggest concern is that of breach of personal data regarding the consumers. As with all other technologies, we can never be sure whether our data is totally secure, so how can the news producers ensure the security and privacy of personal information of their audience. A fairly recent study found that internet users and females in particular are subjected to blackmail and online harassment by their online friends and at times strangers (Shahid, 2018). It is of utmost importance to keep these ground realities in mind before moving towards any new and upcoming technology. News Industry must ensure privacy of their users which they interact with any immersive devices.

Sensitivity of Content

Pakistani has a very emotionally charged culture, with a history of mob displays of aggression and violence if anything is disapproved by the general public. The culture is especially sensitive to topics where religion restricts use of imagery and picture depiction is discouraged. On the other hand, there will be people, who out of their love and respect to religion and religious pilgrimages, might try to reconstruct a certain historic event which will open up many emotionally charged debates.

The producers of Immersive media will need to be extra conscious when choosing subjects on which to produce immersive content on.

Psychological Impact

Certain Immersive experiences maybe too much to endure for people with weak nerves. Reunited (2020) is one such recent experiment where a mother got to say her final goodbyes with her daughter through virtual reality, who died in 2016 (Conte, 2020). Where some may see it as wonders of Immersive Technology, a lot of debates are opening up about eh psychological harm it may bring to the consumers.

In a country like Pakistan, where over sensationalizing tendency is seen in electronic media, we need to be very careful as how to report certain emotionally disturbing news like incidents of violence, child abductions, rape and bomb blasts. Some sort of regulation and check and balance must be in place as the interaction may have serious psychological implications (Cummings, 2016).

Being present in a situation demands our humane side to take action. In an immersive experience, the consumer feels a sudden urge to get up and “save the day”, like in Nonny De la Pena’s project Hunger, viewers are seen expressing helplessness and lack of control, which may lead to guilt and pressure that they didn’t do something that they could. This impact will be enhanced in the case of Pakistan where the majority is not enough technology-literate to understand the situation.

Desensitization Effect

Researches over the years have shown that repeated exposure to violence desensitizes news readers and they are more prone to reading violent news with a more blunted response (Scharrer, 2008). Hence, overexposure has

proven to have desensitization effect on viewers of violent content (Funk, 2005), with low levels of empathy. imagine the adversity if such content is available as an immersive experience. This is a debate as some studies pick this very point up and they argue that the point of Immersive content is to raise empathy, so the consumer is able to put his foot in the victim's shoe.

A lot of empirical research is required to evaluate the impact of exposure, will it create empathy or will it desensitize people.

Will Immersive Journalism be Deepening a Digital Divide?

In a country like Pakistan, technological innovation is specially challenging because there are too many limitations at every stage. An advanced technological intervention like Immersive Journalism will only add to the existing divide between people. People in Pakistan are deprived of many benefits of technology due to a number of reasons including urban-rural divide, gender disparity, income, education, religion and cultural barriers.

The consumers need to produce content that is equally available for all segments of the audience to bridge this technological gap.

Ethical Issues Faced in Fulfilling the Journalist Duty in Immersive Journalism

An exhaustive examination of ethical guidelines of international media outlets and organizations that are using Immersive journalism, suggest that very few have devised any specific guidelines, most are following the existing journalistic guidelines with no mention of any specific technology. (Sánchez Laws, 2019) most media houses and news producers are using guidelines available for visual journalism and guided by their journalistic integrity and the love of technology, they are producing immersive journalistic projects.

Where this futuristic and progressive approach towards technology adoption has benefitted journalists and the field of Immersive Journalism, it has also raised certain questions. Looking at the developments of the past few years, we can observe the following ethical paradoxes presenting themselves in Immersive Journalism Projects.

Accuracy

News industry has always held accuracy of information as the most important trait of their profession. Earlier it was simple to go visit a place and get require information from relevant people and relevant channels and present it as authentic. The same continued in the era of visual journalism and sound bites and camera footages helped convey information with more accuracy than ever. But the concept of accuracy became more complicated in immersive media as the viewer of the content is now active in the visualization of events and accurate conveying of news will also depend upon viewers choice of angle of viewing (Aitamurto, 2019).

A perfectly captured and reconstructed visual may hence fail to communicate the required information or intensity because the viewers angle of viewing was not the one intended for best viewing. A way to address this concern can be that the content producers may guide the viewer through proper instructions in form of text or visual signs.

Objectivity

Another concern that is built-in to the technological structure of the gadgets and content production process is that all content needs to be reconstructed and how should a journalist decide where to use actual footage and images or to manipulate them to achieve most objective reporting. Also, sometimes, actual footage may have unnecessary information, if a journalist trims and skims the actual data in order to make the finished project more comprehensible and message clearer, should be say that the news has been reported objectively? Journalist will need a lot of reinforcement of journalistic guidelines and training in decision making to be able to address these pressing professional practice question as visual journalism allows for little 'fine tuning' but again, how to decide how much is little or lots. (Society of Professional Journalists, 2014)

Confidentiality of Information

Journalist need to be mindful while using data in reproduction of immersive stories. Whether to expose faces, facts, details of the location that are sensitive in nature or fake them and if fake people and places are being used, how will it come down on the storytelling aspect. Journalists need to obtain permissions from sources before including them in a reconstruction. The viewer may be a simple Immersive Media user looking at a news content or he maybe

someone with a malicious intent, looking at a reconstruction to help him/her map the geography of the area to plan his next move.

Whose Story Will be Told

Studies have established Immersive Journalism as a rather strong storytelling tool but we need to consider whose story is being told. Nearly journalistic piece has more than one sides to it. Journalists have always been accused of having biases or being polarized and when doing Immersive Journalism, when the impact is higher, the stakes will also be higher. (Ojebuyi, 2013) The problem with Immersive content is that the inherent liberty and power urges the journalist to produce a perfect story, and in this pursuit for perfection, the journalists is swayed from reproducing the story “as-is” to a version of the story that is “as-if”. Again, only solution is in training and mentoring of the journalist and content producers, they may be made aware of their journalistic duty towards their audience and how it is their duty to stand tall in the name of professional integrity.

Conclusion

Virtual and Augmented reality provides new possibilities to Journalism. However, the implementation has been slow because of high cost of headset technology and the resulting required supplies as well as the need for specialized professionals for handling equipment. Despite this, several media try to incorporate these new possibilities in order to provide the audience with immersive experiences so they can inform them of a more comprehensive and efficient through a first-person interaction. The issue with immersive news content is the authenticity of the content is sleek as an active participant of the story. What you see you believe in, and what you experience can make you focus on that idea. This takes away the scope to avoid conflict of interests and established fairness and accuracy. How successful it can be for the news and mass media is something that will depend upon ethical implications and the simplification of the content consuming process.

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